

MUKIMI'S SOURCE OF LYRICS AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Literature

Keywords: bayaz, manuscript, autograph, literary environment, poet, complex, gazelle, mukhammas (muxammas), letter, past, version, genre, publication.

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Abstract

To investigate the poets' work of our classic literature, you must first collect the literary heritage left by them, as well as identify options and such versions near this. In the past, some artists took care of their fate and collected them. A special place in the history of our literature is the literary heritage of the creators of the Kokand literary environment of the late XIX - early XX centuries. Unfortunately, the great poet of this era, works of Muhammad Aminkhoja Mukimi (1850-1903), was not created in the "Devon" order. However, at the beginning of the 20th century, a collection of poems was published under the name Devon (1907, 1910, 1912, 1913). However, all four of these collections were not organized in accordance with the requirements of the "Devon". Therefore, these collections can be viewed not as "Devon", but as a collection of poems. The manuscript sources of the creativity of Muhammad Aminkhoja Mukimi, the creator of the Kokand literary heritage at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries, kept in manuscript funds of Uzbekistan, were classified and analyzed in this article. Autograph bayazes (bayoz) written by Mukimi's hand were studied and commented about the genre and themes of the poet's works. The newly discovered works of Mukimi are important for studying of the poet's worldview, attitudes towards social reality, the literary and aesthetic world.

Mukimi's works were preserved in various manuscripts and lithography Bayazes, reference books of artists, literary collections of amateurs and some sheets of papers. The merits of Professor G. Karimov in the collection and publication of the works of the poet is great. He had "Collection of Works" (Asarlar to'plami) of Mukimi published four times (1958, 1960, 1973, 1974). Unfortunately, in these publications the works of Mukimi were not published fully and perfectly. As a result of researches by A. Shokirov and O. Dzhuraboev on the manuscripts of the literary heritage of Mukimi received new information about the autograph of the poems of the poet [19, p.159]. Thus, the sources of the manuscript of the work of Muhammad Aminkhoja Mukimi can be classified as following:

- a) The handwriting bayazes, collections of Mukimi and poems on the separate sheets.
- b) The manuscript bayazes and collections created by contemporaries of Mukimi.

The handwriting bayazes, collections and poems of Mukimi and manuscript of the poet on the separate sheets:

In the manuscript fund of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Uzbek Republic.

No. 7521 - manuscript Bayaz. This is a manuscript bayaz of Mukimi. Professor G. Karimov said that in the collection there are 212 poems, 199 of them belongs to Mukimi. The scientist did not add this collection to the manuscript bayazes of the poet [9, p.67].

A. Shokirov mentioned that the volume of poems in the collection is 212, 192 of them belong to Mukimi. [18, p.68].

As a result of further researches, there are not 212 poems in the collection but 228 poetic works, of which 208 were identified as belonging to Mukimi. This Bayaz began to copy in the late 19th century. Although the poet aimed to consolidate his works in various manuscripts, making them in an integral collection but this work has not been completed yet. The fact that many other poems of the author did not enter into it, as well as a lot of empty sheet left at the end of the Bayaz confirms our opinion.

Some poems in the Bayaz were repeatedly edited by the author. There are also two or three versions of the poem. This kind of editorial changes can be found in the text of the manuscript bayazes, as well as the text on the edges. In this Bayaz, the poet wrote a new version of the poem, the recursion of some gazelles and the history of an important event on the edges. Same situation can be found at the page as: 4^a 12^a, 11^a, 13^a, 20^a, 44^a, 45^a, 50^b, 52^b, 56^a, 57^a, 58^a, 62^a, 64^a, 76^b [17, p.223].

Shokirov expressed an opinion for this Bayaz: “From the first page of the Bayaz to 85^a, the texts are written by one hand, and it is not doubt that the changes were entered by Mukimi personally, not from the other person” [16, p.164]. It is based on the analysis of several sources that the writer only wrote the text on page 85^a in the context of one of Mukimi’s contemporaries, the Kokand poet, Mukhsin.

A characteristic feature of Bayaz is that, based on this source, you can reconstruct some of the poems written by the collection of Mukimi. In addition, the poems of the poet about various genres which have been unknown for the society can also be found in the bayaz.

No. 1325 - the manuscript bayaz (bayoz) - was created in Kokand in the end of XIX century. The poets of the XV-XIX centuries are given examples from the works of Navoi, Amiri, Muhyi, Muhayyir, Furkat, Zavki. Professor G. Karimov showed the size of Mukimi’s poems in this bayaz is about 120. However, he also didn’t add this collection to manuscript bayazes of Mukimi. The scientist also does not think about comments on Bayaz Mukimi’s own works. It was commented that: “One hundred and one poem, written in modern manuscript number 1325 from p.264 to 358 in the same order as Devon (7521 manuscript bayaz) unchanged. Moreover, the text of the poems is the same and does not matter [10, p. 96].

Our research shows that the poems in the bayaz are not 120, but 127. In the handwritten script number 7521 there are 110 poems that were recopied in this collection after the edit of the poet.

No. 9309- manuscript bayaz (bayoz) - was copied into Mukimi’s autograph. According to the information on the first page of Bayaz, it was copied in Kokand in 1893. The literary scientist Yo. Iskhakov commented: “We can give an example of the great bayaz of Kokand, created by Mukimi (No. 9309). Mukimi created this bayaz at the end of the 19th century by his friend Abidjan Alam” [4, p.162]. Poems of many poets, such as Jomi, Navoi, Bedil, Gulhaniy, Fazili,

Amiri, Mashrab, Hijlat, Mukimi, Furkat, Zavki, Muhayyir are given in this collection. There are 10 poems and 1 satirical character work of Mukimi in it. At the end of the collection, a document was added in which the honored teacher of Uzbekistan, Pulatzhan Kayumov, the poet Askarali Khamraliyev- Charkhi, the nephew of Mukimi Ruzimuhammad Dustmatov, at the request of Abidjan Alam, they signed the confirmation that created by Mukimi [8, p.11,59]. This fact indicates that Mukimi is the secretary of this Bayaz.

G. Karimov writes about the manuscript number 9309: “10 works of Mukimi are an autograph of the poet’s own hands and therefore should be considered as the most trustworthy and sacramental document” [5, p.267].

In manuscript bayaz No.7688 Mukimi’s poems were copied into his autograph. There are examples of such poems as Jomi, Navoi, Amiri, Muhyi and Mukimi. Bayaz is solid, red with a knitted cover. Texts were copied on shingle papers of Kokand into the table with red, black and blue ink. Texts of poem were written in a small Nastalik letter. Not good preserved, some sheets are torn. Bayaz was created in Kokand at the end of the 19th century and is still not completed. Several pages are empty (127-128-129, 130-131-132-133 pages). The distracting aspect of the researchers, that at the end of the Bayaz Hijri 1327 (1909 AD), signed as Sahib Mullah Abidjan. It turns out that later Sahib Mullah Abidjan aimed to fill the Bayaz with poems of various genres.

By comparing Mukimi’s autograph manuscripts to the text of this bayaz, most of the poems were written on the Mukimi’s handwritten note. There are 39 poetry works in Bayaz, which of these are 32 gazelles, 3 mukhammas, 3 masnawi and 1 murabba (in the hilarious content: “Khan Akam”, “Bachchagar”, “Urug” (The Seed), “Tanobchilar”, “To’y” (The wedding), “Shikoyati bezgak”, “Shamol” (The Wind). In particular, the text of the satiric “Tanobchilar” will be completely 37 bytes in No. 7688 bayaz. In the manuscript No. 5736 and No.309, 317 bayazes it can be found 33 bytes. It is worth noting that this bayaz served as an important source during the restoration of the text of the works of Mukimi in the current edition. *In the Fergana Regional Literary Museum named after Gafur Gulam.*

No. 49.4100- is “Cho‘ntak bayoz” of Mukimi, in that bayaz there is gazelle, murabba and mukhammas of Mukimi. Total 20. Of these poems, 19 were found in Mukimi’s handwriting. 16 of them belongs to Mukimi, 3 of them are gazelles, 4 are murabba and nine are mukhammas (muxammas).

The poems were copied with black ink in the blue, red factory paper in beautiful and medium Nastalik letter. [10, p.44]. Bayaz consists of 39 sheets (p. 79). The first literary scientist, A. Shokirov informed about 10 dastnavis of Mukimi in the Bayaz. [22, p.11].

No. 230.4046 - “Manzumoti forsiy”. The manuscript is a collection which consists of more than ten Persian and Turkish literary figures’ poetry works at the genres of gazelles,

mukhammas (muxammas), masnawi, ruby, problem, fard. The text was copied in a beautiful Nastalik letter in Kokand. Mukimi's autographs are on pages 73-74-, 76-, 77-, 128-, 185-, 189 of the manuscript.

No. 14.4078 - Abdurahmon Jamiy's manuscript book called "Haft Avrang". It was copied by Muhammadkayum Asrori with black ink in Nastalik letter in 1074 year. The autographs of Mukimi can be found at the pages 1, 88, 90, 91, 92, 93, 94, 95, 101, 219 of this bayaz. They are on the edges of the book and belong to Amiri, Majruh, and Mukimi. H. Zarifov, a literary scientist, wrote about two poems in the manuscript of Mukimi.[6, p.166].

No. 7050 - "Shamsil fi-l kavoid ul-mantiqiya" the manuscript work which belongs to Yusuf Baizawi. At the 244 page of this book can be found poem which written in the genre of ta'rix by Mukimi, dedicated to the death of Tursunkhoja. On the 243rd page of the manuscript, with black ink in the Nastalik letter given the following information: "The manuscript book of logic confirms that poem "Dar tarixi vafoti Tursunkhoja eshon" of Mukimi, was Mukimi's own autograph. People's poet of Uzbekistan Askarali Hamroali ugli Charkhiy. Kokand. 02/14/1978.

It can be found 10 (ten) poems of Mukimi which written with his own autograph in the special leaflets in the Kokand Literary Museum, contains poetic works of the poet about various stories[11, p.148].

The manuscript bayaz and collections created by Mukimi's contemporaries

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No. 5666 manuscript bayaz (bayoz). In this bayaz poems of poets such as Fuzuli, Bedil, Jomi, Navoi, Dagi, Zavki, Kori, Furkat, Khoja Khafiz, Fuzuli, Mashrab, Amiri, Furkat, Zari, Mukimi were copied in Nastalik letter. Poems in Uzbek and Persian-Tajik languages. Bayaz was covered hard. Poems are written in red, black ink. Bayaz's secretary is unknown, on page 263 it was written in Hijri 1313. This corresponds to the years 1895-1896 AD. In the collection there are 36 works of Mukimi. Of these, 22 are gazelles (2 in Persian, 1 comic), 10 mukhammas (1 comic), 4 murabba and "Sayohatnoma".

No. 9971 manuscript bayaz (bayoz). It can be found works of Saidido, Bedil, Abdullah Ansari, Nodim, Hijlat, Zari and others in different genres, and the texts were mainly written in Uzbek and Persian-Tajik. Place and secretary are unknown. In Bayaz there is 1 mukhammas (muxammas) of Mukimi (poem titled "Darig'o mulkimiz"), one gazelle ("Dog'men", all versions of the gazelle arbor were edited and modified) and one Murabba, given only one point.

No.4182 – manuscript bayaz (bayoz). There are given poems of Nodira and Nodim Namangani. It is written on page 146 of Bayaz it was written in Namangan in 1314 Hijri (1896

AD). It contains mukhammas (muxammas) of Mukimi (written in Persian-Tajik, “Ash’arho dorad”).

There are examples of works of Fuzuli, Navoi, Furkat, Mukhayir and Mukimi in the **manuscript bayaz (bayoz) No.6352**. Bayaz was covered hard. Well preserved. Texts were copied in black ink. Bayaz’s secretary is unknown. Professor G.Karimov express his opinion about bayaz: “There are 5 (five) works which never seen in other sources before in the bayaz. They are lyric poems in the form of gazelle, murabba” [3, p.456].

In fact, there are not only 5 works of Mukimi, but also 41 works, including 25 gazelles, 10 mukhammas, one of which - “Namear zad”, gazelle of new Sakkai Bukhari. Four murabba’ and two Sayohatnoma (text is fully given). (30 verses from Kokand to Shahimardon and 15 verses from Kokand to Fergana).

Manuscript bayaz (bayoz) No. 9918. It contains poetry works of Navoi, Fuzuli, Mashrab, Furkat, Muhyi, Nasriddin and Mukimi. It was written on the last page of Bayaz in Hijri 1321 (1903 AD). Secretary is unknown. Well preserved. Texts were copied in black ink. It can be found 6 works of Mukimi. These are 3 gazelles, 2 murabba, 1 mukhammas.

No. 7512 – manuscript bayaz (bayoz). Bayaz has a beautiful cover, and its sheets are blue, yellow and red. The first page of the collection is “Bayazi Mukimiy maa Furkat”. But in Bayaz there are samples from Fuzuli, Navoi, Amiri and Akmal. Bayaz’s secretary is unknown. According to the last page of the bayaz, it was copied in Kokand in 1314 AH. It can be found 15 poems of Mukimi. These are 3 mukhammas, 10 gazelles and 2 murabba’. One of them is a 7 couplet gazelle which is unknown for literate person. It was introduced to a gazelle of Navoi which begins with the words: “*Kimsa mendek dahr aro besabru orom o’lmasun*” [13, p. 148].

No. 12195 – Manuscript bayaz (bayoz). “The collection” is called “Majmua’i ashori Mukimi and Furkat”. Bayaz consists of two parts. The first part contains of the works of Mukimi and other poets, the second part includes works of Furkat. According to Bayaz, the collection was created in 1965. The secretary is the famous calligrapher Ahmadjon Sakhhab. Professor G.Karimov wrote about this: “Ahmadjon Sakhhab (1895-1969), as shown, dedicated his life to his literary works, he wrote poetry as an amateur poet” [15, p. 52].

There can be found 39 poems of Mukimi, from them 20 mukhammas, 19 - gazelles (4 new). A.Turdialiyev and S. Eshonov announced one gazelle and 2 mukhammas of Mukimi in the article titled “The recently found poems of Mukimi” on the magazine of “Literature and Art of Uzbekistan” dated April 22, 2011

Manuscript bayaz (bayoz) No.12145 was copied by Muhammed Shakir in 1907. Well preserved. Texts were copied in black ink. Here you can find poems of Fuzuli, Navoi, Furkat and

Mukimi. It should be noted that that the texts of Mukimi's poems in the bayaz were copied completely unchanged from bayaz No.7688. It can be found 21 works of Mukimi, 16 gazelles, 4 mukhammas and one murabba' in it.

No. 9836 – manuscript bayaz (bayoz). On its first page It is written “Ashori Mutafarrika” (scattered poems). Bayaz covered with solid cardboard. The texts are written in black ink. Sheets are blue, yellow and red. Poems are not in order, and blanks are empty. There are examples of works of Jomi, Gazi, Mukimi. There are 9 poems belong to Mukimi, 5 gazelles, 2 mukhammas and 1 murabba'. These poems are found only in empty blanks of bayaz. As for Bayaz, A. Shakirov wrote: “When we read poems in this collection, on page 61 we were attracted by the poem “Muxammasi saylov”. A large volume of eight verses (40 verses) was one of the unknown satiric of Mukimi. Most importantly, the secretary wrote that the date of the poem was “dated on December 18 in 1893”. It can be assumed that this information from the secretary was written in 1893 or earlier [1, p. 231].” We suppose the date of copy is 1891 year. It was signed on August 13, 1891 under the gazelle as “Ohkim, bir dam yuzungni ko'rmasam imkon qani”

No. 10072 Manuscript Bayaz (bayoz). Here are samples of poems by Jomi, Lutfi, Shaido, Amiri, Navoi, Fuzuli, Mashrab and Mukimi. Texts were copied in black ink. The secretary of the Bayaz and the date of copy are not clear. There are 5 works, 4 gazelles and one murabba' of Mukimi in this collection.

No.9966 manuscript bayaz (bayoz). The collection was covered from solid cardboard. According to the information on the first and last pages, the bayaz was written by Azimjon, secretary in Kokand in 1882 [12, p. 211]. There are examples of the works of Amir, Fuzuli, Navoi and Mukimi. The poem of Mukimi can be found written in genre of gazelle.

No. 9098 manuscript bayaz (bayoz). On the last page of It was signed as Kayumkhon Olimboev. But the date of copy is not clear. The collection includes poems by Fuzuli, Navoi, Amiri, Mushfiki and Mukimi. Texts were copied in black ink. There is a mukhammas of Mukimi in the bayaz.

No.1429 manuscript bayaz (bayoz). Bayaz was covered hard. Texts were copied in red, black ink. The year of copy and secretary are unknown. There are works of poets of Kokand. It can be found 6 poems of Mukimi in the bayaz. There are 3 mukhammas, 2 gazelles and 1 murabba.

No. 4179 - Manuscript bayaz (bayoz). The manuscript was a diary of Nodim which confirms the draft verses, written on many leaflets of the bayaz. The materials have been copied since 1892. It contains seven poems of Mukimi (3 comic stories). Professor G.Karimov wrote about bayaz as following: “In addition to being the primary source for studying activity of the poet Nodim, it also provides value-added materials for the study of the literary life of the second half of

the XIX century, the beginning of the 20th century and, on the other, the relations between Nodim and Mukimi, Furkat, Zavki”. [14, p. 52].

Manuscript bayaz (bayoz) No.1821. This bayaz is one of the oldest bayaz and its secretary is Mohammed Tahir. There are examples of such poems of Jomi, Navoi, Bedil, Furkat, Zavki and Mukimi. At the beginning of the collection there is a preface written by the secretary. In the bayaz there are 10 poems of Mukimi. 9 of them are gazelles and 1 mukhammas. The collection was commissioned in Kokand in 1883. There is a five-page review in Persian written by Mukimi in his autograph. A. Murodov and M. Khamidova also commented about this review [2, p. 128].

No.9019 manuscript bayaz (bayoz). The collection was copied in Kokand in 1321, and its secretary is unknown. There are poetry works of Fuzuli, Navoi, Kotibi, Nasriddin, Furkat, Mukhy and Mukimi in the bayaz. There can be found six poems of Mukimi. Of these, 3 gazelles, 2 murabba, 1 mukhammas.

No. 5736 manuscript bayaz. The collection includes poems by poets of Tashkent and Kokand. It should be noted that the text of literary works of Mukimi, which is not found in other sources, is found only in this bayaz. It can be found 42 poems of Mukimi in different genres (two of which are new radif of “makaylik”). O. Tulaboev said that: “The manuscript bayaz (bayoz) No.5736 is the first bayaz of Kami and also is the first source of literary heritage of the poet. It is written on page 471 of his book that it was classified by Abdulkarim Kami in Hijri 1311 (1894 AD). Size 472 pages. There are samples of poems from more than fifty past and contemporary poets in the bayaz. [21, p. 128].

No.7710 manuscript bayaz (bayoz). Secretary of the collection - Karimbek Kami. The cover is thick, red. “Poems in Bayaz begin from page 13. More than sixty poets collected their poems written in Persian and Turkish in Bayaz. In other words, in 1895 the title “Murabba dar tarifi maktab” was published in the newspaper of “Turkistan Region’s Newspaper”, but in 1902 there was no manzuma titled “Yaxshi” (Good) which published in this newspaper. This is the basis of this bayaz was written between 1895-1902 years. [22]

“In the bayaz there are three poems of Mukimi, those based on the mukhammas of Jami, Furkat and Amiri. However, the text of this mukhammas (muxammas) is not fully provided. [22, p. 17].

At all, the text of the poems in the manuscript of Mukimi has not yet been fully investigated. In particular, some poems are still not entered into the scientific use. From this point of view, the autograph bayazes of Mukimi number 7521, 1325, 9309, 49.4100, 7688, written in his own handwriting, are the main source of the scientific and critical text of the poet’s works.

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